

Stress tolerance—advance soils

Comparative studies of germination and seedling growth of some salt-tolerant selections at different salinity levels

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Ten salt-tolerant selections, identified and developed in the IRRRI-India Collaborative Program at Kakdwip, were tested for their tolerance for high salinity during germination and seedling stages.

These included eight accessions, two traditional improved selections (Hamilton, from local variety Nona Bokra, and Matla, from local variety Getu) widely grown under tidal wetland situation, a resistant check (SR26-B), and a susceptible check (Jaya).

We arranged 50 seeds of each line on glass plates and conducted a germination test following the method of Dasgupta et al (1976). In separate procedures, the bottoms of the glass plates were immersed in one of the

following treatments: distilled water (T1), saline water from a local estuary diluted with distilled water to have an electrical conductivity (EC) of 7.8 dS/m (T2), and saline water from the estuary without dilution that had an EC of 14.6 dS/m (T3). The experiment was replicated three times.

Effects of salt concentrations on plant characters were analyzed statistically (see table).

Germination was significantly reduced in only two entries—IR52712-B-B-33-B-B-CN-3 and IR49737-B-B-29-B-B-CN-1—when salinity was increased from 0 to 7.8 dS/m. Germination was significantly reduced in selections IR52712-B-B-33-B-B-CN-3, IR52713-B-B-19-B-B-CN-4, IR49737-B-B-29-B-B-CN-1, and SR26-B at higher salinity (EC 14.6 dS/m). Germination percentage in other entries remained almost constant across salinity levels.

Significant increase in root length at 7.8 dS/m was observed in IR4630-22-5-1-CN-940, IR51194-CN-930-44-16-B, and IR52713-B-B-19-B-B-CN-4, but at

14.6 dS/m, root growth was significantly reduced in IR52713-B-B-19-B-B-CN-4. Root growth was almost unaffected—even at the high salinity level—in Hamilton, Matla, and IR52712-B-B-33-B-B-CN-3. Root growth decreased steadily in IR31376-1-2-2-2-4-1 with the increase in salinity level.

Shoot length generally decreased with increasing salinity; this tendency was most conspicuous in Jaya and IR31376-1-2-2-2-4-1. Shoot growth remained almost unaffected across salinity levels in other entries.

Dry matter accumulation in general was not affected by salinity, except in LR52712-B-B-33-B-B-CN-3, IR52713-B-B-19-B-B-CN-4, and Hamilton. In LR49737-B-B-29-B-B-CN-1 and SR26-B, it increased constantly with the increase in salinity.

IR4630-22-5-1-CN-940 was comparatively more tolerant of high levels of salinity during germination and seedling growth stages than the other entries. ■

Comparative performance of entries under different salinity levels^a during germination and seedling stages.

Entry	Comparative performance with respect to character														
	Germination (%)			Mean root length (cm)			Mean shoot length (cm)			Dry wt per plant (mg)			Normal seedlings germinated (%)		
	T1	T2	T3	T1	T2	T3	T1	T2	T3	T1	T2	T3	T1	T2	T3
IR13198-66-2-CN 939-2-1	84.4	82.2	81.2	12.1	14.7	11.2	6.5	6.8	5.4	12.83	14.87	11.67	80.3	75.3	41.6
IR4630-22-5-1-CN-940	88.1	89.3	86.0	10.2	16.3	14.3	6.8	8.1	8.2	14.10	16.03	13.70	85.7	83.5	71.0
IR51194-CN-930-44-16-8	84.1	87.2	82.2	8.9	14.4	15.7	6.2	8.7	7.8	12.60	14.40	12.33	84.3	84.6	55.4
IR41213-6-6-3-B-6-CN-107	93.5	92.7	92.7	16.8	13.7	13.7	11.3	9.6	9.5	32.60	39.43	32.20	89.6	78.0	69.2
IR31376-1-2-2-2-4-1	90.4	87.7	86.0	19.1	15.7	12.4	12.6	10.5	8.2	27.07	25.87	22.70	81.6	84.5	77.4
IR52712-B-B-33-6-6-CN-3	81.8	74.0	65.0	6.9	8.3	9.9	7.0	6.8	5.1	21.09	21.70	12.03	71.8	62.7	54.0
IR52713-6-B-19-6-B-CN-4	91.0	91.0	82.5	6.8	11.2	6.4	6.3	6.5	4.9	20.23	20.17	9.50	92.0	84.7	56.4
IR49737-6-6-29-6-B-CN-1	94.3	72.8	69.9	8.6	9.8	7.4	5.7	5.6	4.8	28.23	31.33	32.46	83.4	65.6	68.1
Hamilton	92.2	89.5	87.3	15.3	14.2	15.8	11.6	11.2	9.7	19.80	12.33	10.27	76.6	77.2	58.4
Matla	95.2	91.6	90.2	15.2	18.7	14.9	9.0	12.0	8.1	30.77	32.93	32.80	80.5	83.1	67.7
Jaya (susceptible check)	89.1	90.5	82.2	12.1	13.4	9.1	7.5	5.1	3.6	38.23	36.70	29.77	79.9	74.3	60.9
SR26-B (resistant check)	93.1	88.4	83.9	16.3	17.3	13.4	9.4	9.8	7.3	44.63	46.97	49.37	78.1	74.6	62.2
CV (%) for treatments		2.2			9.3			10.4			8.7			3.7	
CV (%) for selections		3.0			16.6			13.6			10.5			2.9	
LSD (treatments) at P (0.01)		7.1			4.4			3.1			8.1			10.3	
LSD (selections) at P (0.01)		5.4			4.4			2.4			5.5			4.5	

^a T1 = distilled water, T2 and T3 = saline water collected from local estuary with EC value of 7.8 and 14.6 dS/m, respectively.